

**INFLUENCE OF *FADAMA NSE BEBE* TELEVISION PROGRAMME ON
SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN ONDO STATE**

Tosin Adesile (PhD)
Department of Mass Communication
Crawford University, Igbesa, Ogun State
&

Funmilayo Ikueduranni
Department of Mass Communication
Elizade Univeristy, Ilara Mokin, Ondo State

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable agricultural development is crucial to Nigeria's pursuit of food security, environmental stewardship, and rural economic transformation. Mass Media is believed to be one of the key drivers of this noble initiative particularly agricultural television programmes which have emerged as influential platforms for disseminating knowledge and encouraging the adoption of sustainable farming practices. This study investigated the influence of *Fadama Nse Bebe*, an agricultural television programme, on sustainable agricultural development among farmers in Ondo State, Nigeria. Anchored in the Development Media Theory, the study explores how media exposure influences awareness, knowledge dissemination, and behavioural change in agricultural practices. A survey research design was employed, using purposive and multi-stage sampling techniques to select 384 respondents across five Local Government Areas: Akure South, Akure North, Ifedore, Ondo East, and Ondo West. The study assessed farmers' awareness, viewership, and exposure to *Fadama Nse Bebe* as well as their adoption of the practices promoted. Findings reveal a high level of awareness and regular viewership of the programme among respondents. Notably, a significant number of farmers reported applying the knowledge acquired from the programme to improve their farming methods, particularly in areas of sustainable land use and resource management. Statistical analysis indicated a strong, positive correlation between programme exposure and adoption of sustainable agricultural techniques. The study concludes that agricultural television programming constitutes a viable tool for promoting sustainable agriculture. It recommends consistent programme scheduling and improved funding mechanisms to enhance media advocacy as well as address irregularities in broadcast, thereby maximizing its developmental impact.

Keywords: Agricultural Television, Fadama Nse Bebe, Media Influence, Sustainable Farming

Introduction

It is impossible to overstate the role that the media play in agro-economy, sustainable agriculture, and national development. One of the most important channels for providing farmers with the necessary farming instructions is the mass media. The well-known media like radio, television, and newspapers remain essential for educating farmers about new technologies, government initiatives, and sustainable practices. This access to information can significantly enhance agricultural productivity and efficiency (Rahul & Mahendra, 2024; Nawab et al., 2020)

The media facilitate educational programme that inform farmers about improved farming techniques and pest management strategies (Tambo et al., 2023). Through raising awareness of contemporary agricultural practices, media help farmers adapt to changing conditions and improve their yields (Negi, 2023). The media function of highlighting critical issues faced by the agricultural sector, such as climate change and financial challenge, draws the attention of government and policymakers to these problems, and gain the necessary supportive measures for farmers (Kedir, 2020).

Nevertheless, it is important to know that media are essential in advancing cutting-edge farming methods over the world. The media has used a variety of platforms and techniques to spread important information, educate farmers, encourage community involvement, push for legislative changes, and incorporate technology to promote agricultural development (Nwibo et al.; 2022). Another primary way the media promote innovative agricultural practices is through information dissemination, as mass media, including radio, television, and print, serve as a vital avenue for transmitting agricultural information (Manyasa & Mtenga, 2017). Also, through media effort, agriculturalists receive updates on weather forecasts, market trends, and new farming techniques, which helps optimise their operations and improve yields. (Akinbile & Oladele, 2016).

Sustainable agriculture offers a lifeline, a way to feed the world's billions while preserving our planet for generations to come. In essence, sustainable agriculture refers to a set of farming practices that aim to meet our current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs (Aninver Development Project, 2024)

Sustainable agriculture practices and methods include practical application of a wide range of practices such as crop rotation which is a fundamental practice in sustainable agriculture (Tracextech, 2023). Crop rotation involves the systematic planting of different crops in a specific order in the same field over successive seasons (Pandey, 2024). By diversifying crops through practices like crop rotation, farmers can often increase their overall yield while simultaneously reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and other chemical inputs, contributing to a more sustainable agricultural system (Mihrete & Mihretu, 2025).

The practice of conservation tillage minimises soil disturbance, preserving soil structure and organic matter is viable method of sustainable agriculture. No-till and reduced-till methods avoid traditional ploughing and are effective in reducing soil erosion, conserving water, and mitigating carbon emissions. These practices are especially valuable in regions prone to soil erosion. (Sustainable Agriculture Research & Education Programme, 2021).

An essential component of sustainable agriculture is effective water management. Water waste is decreased by using water-efficient irrigation techniques like drip irrigation and precision farming, which guarantee that water is delivered straight to the plant root zone. These methods encourage responsible water usage and aid in the preservation of water resources (Ray & Majumder, 2024).

The *Fadama Nse Bebe*, is a television Programme aired on Ondo State Radiovision Corporation with the objective of improving farmers' knowledge and skills about sustainable agriculture, increasing agricultural productivity, and promoting an increase in the income of water and land resources users on a sustainably basis (Project Implementation Manual, 2008). The programme equally seeks to educate, sensitise and inform the Fadama farmers, relevant stakeholders as well as the public about activities of the Fadama III Project. The television programme is sponsored by Ondo State Fadama Coordination Office and broadcast in Yoruba language (Ondo State Fadama Coordination Office, 2013). The programme, which is aired between year 2012 to 2024 also features experts and Fadama beneficiary farmers sharing knowledge and experiences on best practices in agriculture (Ondo State Fadama Coordination Office, 2013). From the foregoing, this study seeks to investigate the influence of *Fadama Nse Bebe* Television programme on sustainable agricultural development in Ondo state, as it has underscored the fact that there is a working nexus between the media and sustainable agriculture.

Statement of Problem

In light of the growing global population and the severity of climate change, resilient agricultural practices are becoming more essential today. Sustainable agricultural development is important in a nation where there problems of food security, environmental degradation, and rural poverty (Sustainable Agricultural Network, 2023; Aninver Development Project, 2024).

According to data from the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 82 million Nigerians lived on less than \$1 a day in 2020, with rural areas being disproportionately affected (Aljazera, 2020). Furthermore, emphasising the need to have a result-oriented agricultural practice, Izuchukwu et al. (2023) noted:

Because of its heavy reliance on rain-fed systems, the nation's agricultural industry is susceptible to the effects of climate change. In order to maintain sustainable livelihoods, improve food security, and lessen the consequences of climate change in rural Nigeria, especially in areas like Ondo State, it is becoming increasingly important to develop and encourage robust agricultural practices. (pp. 1-27)

As a vital conduit between farmers, policymakers, and agricultural specialists, the media is expected to drum support for sustainable agriculture in Nigeria. Thus, this research investigated the role of television in influencing the practice of sustainable agriculture development using *Fadama Nse Bebe* Television Programme and Ondo State as a study.

Research Questions

The following questions guided this study

- i. How well are the farmers exposed to *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme?
- ii. How has *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme improved farmers' knowledge about sustainable agricultural practices in Ondo State?
- iii. What are the various ways the television programme has encouraged farmers in sustainable agricultural practices?
- iv. What are the challenges associated with the television programme in encouraging sustainable agriculture among farmers?

Theoretical Framework

The Development Media Theory anchored the study.

2.2.1 Development Media Theory

The study's theoretical foundation was established through the use of Development Media Theory, which offers valuable insights into the work. The limits of the traditional Four Theories of the Press, which were created by Siebert, Peterson, and Schramm in 1956, gave rise to Development Media Theory in the 1960s. Western media experiences and ideas served as the primary foundation for these early theories, which included authoritarian, libertarian, social responsibility, and Soviet/communist views. In Africa, Asia, and Latin America, where the media landscape was supposed to act as a catalyst for socio-economic development and national integration, scholars and practitioners noted that these models did not sufficiently represent the realities and needs of recently independent countries (Siebert et al., 1956).

During the post-colonial era, when many Global South countries were undergoing political upheaval and aiming for rapid modernisation, the need for a new theory became more apparent. These countries needed a media infrastructure that could actively support a variety of objectives, including health awareness, literacy promotion, development communication, nation-building, and agricultural improvement. In this setting, the media was seen as a developmental tool that could help governments accomplish public policy goals rather than only as a vehicle for commercial profit or watchdog journalism (McQuail, 1987).

Development Media Theory was formally introduced by famous media theorist Dennis McQuail in his seminal work *Mass Communication Theory: An Introduction*. He maintained that, in accordance with nationally set policies, the media should embrace and perform constructive developmental duties in developing countries. According to McQuail (1987), these responsibilities include encouraging economic growth, maintaining national cohesion, educating the populace, and aiding in cultural preservation. According to the argument, in order to guarantee that media content is in line with these developmental aims, the state may rightfully impose restrictions on press freedom.

Development Media Theory advocates for a normative perspective that views it as an active participant in national development, which is one of the main tenets of the Development Media Theory. That the media should prioritise content that promotes economic growth, political

stability, education, and cultural cohesion in order to support the national development agenda. In this context, the media is expected to collaborate with the state and development institutions in order to disseminate information that promotes modernisation and progress, rather than operating with total autonomy as in the libertarian model (McQuail, 2010).

Another fundamental principle of the Development Media Theory is that, in order to assist the national development agenda, the media should give priority to content that fosters political stability, economic progress, education, and cultural cohesion. Instead of working independently as in the libertarian model, the media is supposed to cooperate with the government and development organisations in this setting to spread knowledge that encourages modernisation and advancement (McQuail, 2010).

Effective communication strategies have been crucial in improving agricultural practices in Nigeria, where agriculture is both a vital economic sector and a pillar of food security. DMT provides a compelling framework for using media to promote sustainable agricultural development. For example, a study on cassava farmers found that those exposed to agricultural innovations through videos and demonstrations had significantly higher adoption rates of improved weed management practices than those who were not. This highlights the media's ability to influence farmers to adopt better practices (Atser et al., 2022). A key relevance of DMT to this study is the media's obligation to serve as a conduit between the general public and decision-makers. For the dissemination of agricultural knowledge in rural Nigeria, media is a vital means. The effectiveness of agricultural communication can be increased by addressing these issues by translating information into local settings and broadcasting in indigenous languages (Rahul & Mahendra, 2024).

Research Design

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews to examine the influence of *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme on sustainable agricultural practice. The qualitative interview method was used in this study, as it enables the researcher to collect data about people's opinions, attitudes, behaviours, preferences, and perceptions regarding a certain topic or subject matter in a methodical manner.

Population of the Study

The study examined Fadama farmers watching the *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme on Ondo State Radiovision Corporation within the catchment areas of the television station in the central senatorial district of five local government areas of Akure South, Akure North, Ifedore, Ondo East, and Ondo West in the state's central senatorial district, thus making the main scope of study. The 38,333 farmers that participated in the Fadama III Project are thus the main population of this work (Ondo State Fadama III Project, 2013).

Table 1: Distribution of FADAMA Beneficiary Farmers in Ondo State

S/N	LGA	No. of FCA REGISTERED	Register No of FUGs	No. of Male	No. of female	TOTAL
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1	AKOKO NORTH/EAST	10	84	881	633	1,541
2	AKOKO NORTH/WEST	10	142	1,047	1,292	2,639
3	AKOKO SOUTH/EAST	6	51	765	612	1,377
4	AKOKO SOUTH/WEST	9	72	1,080	864	1,944
5	AKURE NORTH	10	116	763	661	1,424
6	AKURE SOUTH	11	171	1,636	1,748	3,384
7	ESE ODO	11	132	1,980	1,584	3,654
8	IDANRE	7	45	675	540	1,215
9	IFEDORE	9	104	932	592	1,524
10	ILAJE	9	135	1,751	1,123	2,874
11	ILE OLUJI/O	10	99	1,098	961	2,059
12	IRELE	8	72	1,224	864	2,088
13	ODIGBO	7	59	597	333	930
14	OKITIPUPA	12	137	2,136	1,923	4,059
15	ONDO EAST	7	73	1,241	949	2,190
16	ONDO WEST	6	52	505	423	928
17	OSE	8	83	1,245	996	2,241
18	OWO	10	137	1,943	736	2,679
19	TOTAL	160	1764	21,499	16,834	38,333

Source: 8th joint FGN/World Bank Supervision Mission. November, 2013.

Sample Size

The researcher determined 384 as the sample size for this study using the Cochran (1963) equation ‘1’ which yields a representative sample for population that are large and it is as follows:

$$n = \frac{[Z/2]^2 (p q)}{e^2} \quad n = \frac{[Z/2]^2 (P) (1-P)}{e^2}$$

Where: n= sample size, Z²= confidence level, p= rate of occurrence or prevalence (the estimated proportion of an attribute that is present in a population), q= complement of p and e= margin of error. Therefore;

$$n = \frac{[1.96]^2 0.5 (1 - 0.5)}{0.05^2} \quad n = \frac{3.8416 (0.25)}{0.0025} \quad n = 384.16. =384$$

Therefore, the sample size (n) is 384.

3.4 Sampling Technique

The multi-stage sampling technique was used for this study. Here are the details of the steps:

Stage One: The researcher employed purposive sampling technique to select respondents within the determined coverage area of OSRC, which are Akure South, Akure North, Ifedore, Ondo East and Ondo West. (Ondo State Radiovision corporation, 2025)

Stage Two: The cluster sampling method: the researcher selected the clusters that fall within the coverage areas from the data of FADAMA beneficiary (as indicated above in 3.2)

Stage Three: The proportional random sampling was utilised to allocate the questionnaire to respondents in the selected local government areas.

The questionnaire distribution was determined by the following equations:

$$nh = (Nh / N) * n$$

Where nh is the sample size for stratum h, Nh is the population size for stratum h, N is total population size, and n is total sample size (Stat Trek, 2014, p.1, in Nwangwuma, 2014).

That is: (local govt. ÷ FADAMA farmers × sample size= allocated questionnaire).

From the table 2. below, the *allocation of questionnaires* is as follows:

Table 2.

OSRC Area of Coverage by District	Selected Local Government Area	Population of Selected FADAMA Farmers	Number of Allocated Questionnaire
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Akure South	3,384	120
Akure North	1,425	50
Ifedore	2874	102
Ondo East	2190	78
Ondo West	982	34
Total	10,801	384

Source: 2025 Survey

The table shows the allocation of questionnaire copies based on the strength of the selected state capitals using the proportionate sampling technique

For the in-depth interview, the researcher followed the tenets of purposive techniques to recruit the interview participants. This comprised two management staff of OSRC and two FADAMA officials.

Instrument for Data Collection

For the quantitative data, questionnaire was used as the primary instrument. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) sections; first section contains questions relating to personal demographics of respondents, while the second section elicits responses that bordered on the key research objectives that were developed for the study.

The questionnaires were administered with use of physical administration which enables the researcher to reach the respondents through assigned Community Facilitators. The questionnaires contain close-ended questions using the ‘5-point Likert measurement scale’ items. The interview guide, which included both auxiliary and open-ended questions, was the qualitative tool. Semi-structured and follow-up questions were included in the set of questions. In order to capture participants in their natural setting, the interview was audio recorded.

Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

Data collection and cleaning; Microsoft excel was used to enter, clean and structure the data. Descriptive analysis; Excel (pivot table and chart) for demographic data. Power Bi for visualisation of response. Statistical Package for Social Sciences, (SPSS): for frequency tables, research questions testing. The tool (SPSS) gave a clear representation of the research methods used for collecting data. The data were presented in tables and percentages. Under each of the study's research questions, there was a connecting, distinct discussion subheading that discussed the findings in light of previous research (Stage & Manning, 2003). Sufficient interpretations of the statements made by the participants were established.

Results and Findings

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents revealed that the majority of practicing farmers are between 50-69 years old (47%). It showed the distribution of gender (slightly more males 61% than females). Educational levels (with secondary school being the most common) and the majority are Christians (75%). The parity distribution shows that 38% of the farmers are self-employed/farmer, while 28% are full time farmers. 10% of respondent were civil servants/farmers.

Respondents' exposure to the *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme indicated that a majority of the respondents (60%) have watched the programme, and there was a general perception that the programme was popular among farmers in Ondo State.

Table 3: Exposure to *Fadama Nse Bebe*

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Have you ever watched <i>Fadama Nse Bebe</i> TELEVISION programme on OSRC?	Yes	231	60%
	No	153	40%
Total		384	100%
<i>Fadama Nse Bebe</i> is a very popular television programme among farmers in Ondo state.	Strongly Agree	81	21%
	Agree	153	40%
	Neutral	61	16%
	Disagree	61	16%
	Strongly Disagree	28	7%
Total		384	100%

Source: 2025 Survey

A significant proportion of the respondents reported adopting lessons from the programme in their farming practices, as 78% of the respondent either strongly agree, agree or neutral.

Table 4: Adoption of Sustainable Practices from *Fadama Nse Bebe*

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
<i>I usually adopt lessons learned from Fadama Nse Bebe TELEVISION Programme in my farming activities.</i>	Strongly Agree	103	27%
	Agree	149	39%
	Neutral	45	12%

	<i>Disagree</i>	61	16%
	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	26	6%
<i>Total</i>		384	100%

Source: Survey 2025

The television programme, *Fadama Nse Bebe* proved to be quite successful in changing agricultural practice. In sharp contrast to the 40% of non-viewers who implemented sustainable agriculture methods, almost 80% of those who saw the programme did so. The statistical significance of this difference ($p < 0.001$) indicates a strong causal association between exposure to the programme and the adoption of better behaviours.

Increased motivation was also strongly associated with programme’s viewership. It was discovered that viewers were twice as inclined than non-viewers to embrace sustainable farming methods. A Mann-Whitney U-test was used to check this, and the results demonstrated strong statistical significance ($p < 0.001$), highlighting the psychological influence of the programme on its viewers.

Motivation for sustainable agriculture was found to be significantly predicted by two main elements. First, there was a significant influence from programme perception, or how favourably viewers viewed the show ($\beta = +0.65$). Second, and perhaps more importantly, the number of viewers of the show was a robust predictor ($\beta = +1.20$), suggesting that farmers' increased motivation was directly fuelled by repeated exposure to the content.

Important obstacles were found that restrict the programme's overall efficacy and the wider adoption of sustainable practices, despite its demonstrated impact. 65% (Sixty-five percent) of respondents said they had trouble consistently accessing the television show because of electricity problems, particularly in remote locations with inadequate infrastructure. Furthermore, according to 84% of respondents, they had financial difficulties adopting or putting into practice the sustainable farming methods that the programme promotes, not because they couldn't afford or own a television. Affording high-quality seeds, fertiliser, irrigation supplies, and other inputs required for contemporary, sustainable farming are examples of these difficulties.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1:

How well farmers are exposed to the *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme?

The data revealed that a significant majority (60%) of the farmers have watched the programme on OSRC. This suggests a relatively high level of exposure among the farming community in Ondo State. Additionally, the perception of the programme's popularity among farmers further supports this, with 61% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that *Fadama Nse Bebe* is a popular television programme among farmers in Ondo State.

Research Question 2:

How has the *Fadama Nse Bebe* programme improved farmers' knowledge about sustainable agricultural practices?

The study indicated that a substantial proportion of the farmers acknowledge that sustainable agricultural practice is pertains to soil conservation and health (80%), Water management (75%), Biodiversity conservation (70%), Climate Change Mitigation and Adaption (65%), Integrated Pest Management (60%), Crop Rotation and Intercropping (85%), Irrigation Practices (70%), and Use of Organic Fertilizers (75%). While this high level of awareness cannot be solely attributed to the television programme. Farmers must have a thorough understanding of sustainable agricultural methods since they have a direct impact on the long-term profitability, productivity, and environmental health of their operations.

The study also revealed that most significant respondents reported that sustainable agricultural practice pertains to water conservation (79%), Irrigation System (84%), Organic Farming and organic fertilizer (85%), Crop Rotation (79%), Climate Change Mitigation and Adaption (80%) were talked about during the programme. It suggests that farmers in the State possess a good understanding of at least one key aspect of sustainable agriculture through the television programme.

Research Question 3:

In what ways in which the television programme has encouraged farmers in sustainable agricultural practices?

The data revealed that a significant percentage (66%) of the respondents reported that they usually adopt lessons learned from the "*Fadama Nse Bebe*" television programme in their farming activities. This implies that the television programme was indeed influencing farmers' behaviour and encouraging the adoption of sustainable practices.

Research Question 4:

What are the challenges associated with the television programme effectiveness in encouraging sustainable agriculture among farmers.

The study identified several key obstacles. These include challenges with television reception (32%), lack of electricity (65%), limited broadcast time (28%), and inadequate awareness (40%). Lack of electricity appears to be the most significant challenge, hindering farmers' ability to access the programme.

The study also outlined some other challenges respondents face in applying sustainable agricultural practices learned in the *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme to include lack of Finance 84%, followed by limited Access to Equipment 65%, Insufficient knowledge/skill 47%, Environmental factors (weather) 40% and Problem of pest 30%. The lack of continuity of the television programme, though coming from only one respondent interviewed suggested a strong factor that can be responsible for lack of knowledge retention on subject matter of sustainable agriculture.

However, on the key lessons gained from the television programme, pest control method, irrigation system, new technology, access to farm input, climate change, access to market outlets, water

conservation, record keeping and group dynamics attracted low percentage in the rating of the key lesson learnt from *Fadama Nse Bebe*.

Conclusion

Based on the result of the study conducted, farmers in Ondo State have been significantly impacted by the television show *Fadama Nse Bebe* in terms of sustainable agricultural development. The vast majority of respondents were aware of the programme, and many of them admitted to learning important information about important facets of sustainable agriculture, including irrigation systems, water conservation, and climate change. Additionally, a sizable portion of farmers stated that they frequently implement the programme's principles, underscoring its usefulness and influence. Through empowerment and educational materials, the programme was also proven to have a favourable impact on farmers' revenue.

However, despite widespread knowledge and awareness, there is still a noticeable lack of comprehension of certain crucial elements of sustainable agriculture, such as sophisticated water saving techniques, pest management techniques, and more profound climate change concerns.

Also respondents reported that they faced challenges in applying sustainable agricultural practices learned in the *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme to include lack of finance, followed by limited access to equipment, insufficient knowledge/skill, environmental factors (weather) and problem of pest.

Consistent learning and programme continuity were also reportedly hampered by broadcast disruptions, which were mostly caused by financial difficulties. Further restricting the programme's accessibility and efficacy, around 65% of respondents mentioned an intermittent electrical supply as a major obstacle to participation. The issue of uneven broadcasting because of financial limitations was also brought to light, resulting in disruptions that impact the learning process and continuity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were suggested to further enhance the influence of the *Fadama Nse Bebe* television programme and promote the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices among farmers in Ondo State:

To assure the programme's continuous broadcast, the government should provide steady funding. Partnerships with agricultural organisations and sponsors in the private sector could offer extra money to lessen an excessive dependence on governmental assistance.

The agricultural television programme should look for partnerships with important players in the agricultural sector, such as agribusiness companies, international development organisations, and government agencies like the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, in order to guarantee adequate funding and ongoing broadcasting, raising farmers' awareness beyond the current 60%. These collaborations may offer recurring financial assistance in the form of grants, sponsorships, or advertising. Stakeholders receive a platform to advertise their programmes, goods, or services specifically designed for farmers in exchange.

It is recommended that provision of necessary media advocacy and relevant training can assist farmers to deliver better agricultural dividend. In this wise, capacity building and farmer education should be pursued. There should be a pressing need for regular training and workshops tailored to the needs of farmers. Extension services should be strengthened to provide hands-on demonstrations and follow-up support on critical aspects such as pest management, water-saving techniques, and the implications of climate change on agriculture. All these efforts should be relayed and linked to television programme.

Through cooperatives or rental programme, stakeholders should give priority to the supply and distribution of reasonably priced, contemporary farming equipment. Agricultural and allied agencies like ministry of environment should be encouraged to educate farmers on integrated pest management (IPM) and ecologically friendly techniques. The television programme *Fadama Nse Bebe* should also think about improving and broadening its content to make sense of complicated but important topics including water conservation techniques, pest management, and climate change adaptation. To fill in the identified knowledge gaps, content should be made easier to acquire and understand.

REFERENCES

- Akinbile, L.A., & Oladele, O. I. (2016). The Role of Mass Media in Agricultural Development in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 20(1), 1-11.
- Aljazeera. (2020). Forty Percent of Nigerians Live Below the Poverty Line: Report. <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2020/5/4/forty-percent-of-nigerians-live-below-the-poverty-linereport#:~:retrieved on 17th Jnmuary, 2025>.
- Atser, G., Dixon, A., Ekeleme, F., Hauser, S, Fadaïro, O., Adekoya, A., Ayanwale, A.B., Agada, M., Oladokun, I., Akpu, P., Sanni, L., Pypers, P., Ampadu-Boakye, T., & Vanlauwe, B. (2022). The Effect of Communication Media on the Uptake of Agricultural Innovations in Selected States of Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*. Vol 29, Issue 5
- Chukwu, C.O. (2015). The Dynamics of Communication in Agricultural Development. The Case of the South-Eastern States of Nigeria. Department of Mass Communication Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki-Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development Studies* Vol.1, No.2, pp.1-.17. www.eajournals.org
- Izuchukwu A., Nzechie, O., Obiorah, J., & Ogar, E.E. (2023). Analysing the Critical Impact of Climate Change on Agriculture and Food Security in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* DOI:10.56201/ijaes.v9.no4.2023. pp. 1.27
- Kedir, U. (2020). Agricultural Broadcasting Media (ABM) for Agricultural Developments and Structural Change Within and Across the Countries: A Review. *International Journal of Research Studies in Biosciences (IJRSB)* Volume 8, Issue 4, 2020, PP 26-33 ISSN No. (Online) 2349-0365 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0365.0804004> www.arcjournals.org
- Manyasa, E. O., & Mtenga, L. A. (2017). The Role of Mass Media in Promoting Agricultural Innovation among Smallholder Farmers in Tanzania. *Journal of Agricultural and Extension Education*, 23(2), 147-162.

- McQuail, D. (1987). *Mass Communication Theory: An Introduction* (2nd ed.). London: Sage Publications.
- Mihrete, T.B., & Mihretu, F.B. (2025). Crop Diversification for Ensuring Sustainable Agriculture, Risk Management and Food Security. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.202400267>
- Munene, M.W., & Mberia, H. (2016). Effects of Television Agricultural Shows on Small-Scale Farmers' Information Need in Kenya: A Case Study of Kikuyu Sub-County. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. DOI: 10.6007/IJARBSS/v6-i4/2084 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v6-i4/2084>
- Nazari, M.R., & Hassan, M. S. H. (2020). The Role of Television in the Enhancement of Farmers' Agricultural Knowledge. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development* Vol. 8 (3), pp. 001-006, <https://www.internationalscholarsjournals.com/articles/the-role-of-television-in-the-enhancement-of-farmers-agricultural-knowledge.pdf>
- Negi, S. (2023). Role of Mass Media in Agriculture. *International Journal of Novel Research and Development*. Volume 8, Issue 7. <https://www.ijnrd.org/papers/IJNRD2307399.pdf>
- Nwibo, S. U., Mbam, B. N., Odoh, N. E., Egwu, P. N., Uloh, F. U., & Oken, D. E. (2022). Influence of Mass Media Promoted Agricultural Programme on Arable Crop Production in Ezza North Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Agricultural Journal* Volume 53 Number 1 A Pg. 388-395. <http://www.ajol.info/index.php/naj> <https://www.naj.asn.org.ng>
- Ogunsola J.O., Ogunsola A.J., Alarape A.B., Oloba O.G., & Osalusi C.S. (2019). Effectiveness of broadcast Agricultural Programme on Agricultural Development among Farmers in Akoko South West Local Government Area of Ondo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology (IJEAB)* Vol-4, Issue-5. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijeab.45.16>
- Olurinola, I. O., & Osabuohien, E., (2021). Socio-Economic and Environmental Issues: Implications for Food Security in Nigeria. *CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 59(4), 197-219.
- Oresanya, O., & Olajide, R. (2023). Farmers' Propensity to Use Reality Television Shows for Information on Climate-Smart Agriculture Strategies in South-Western Nigeria. *Agricultura Tropica et Subtropica*, 56(1), 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ats-2023-0008>
- Rahul, K.D., & Mahendra, K. Y. (2024). Impact of Mass Media in Agriculture: An Overview. *International Journal on Agricultural and Biological Research*. Volume 40, Issue 4. <https://www.abrinternationaljournal.org/articles/impact-of-mass-media-in-agriculture-an-overview-110379.html>
- Ray, S., & Majumder, S. (2024). Water Management in Agriculture: Innovations for Efficient Irrigation. In book: *Modern Agronomy* (pp.169-185) Publisher: International Books & Periodical Supply Service
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations* (5th ed.). New York: Free Press.
- Tambo, J. A., Mugambi, I., Onyango, D.O., Uzayisenga, B., & Romney, D. (2023). Using Mass Media Campaigns to Change Pesticide Use Behaviour among Smallholder Farmers in East Africa. *Journal of Rural Studies*. Volume 99, April 2023, Pages 79-91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.03.001>

Tracex tech. (2023). 5 Benefits of Crop Rotation for Sustainable Agriculture. [https://tracex tech.com/5-benefits-of-crop-rotation-for-sustainable agriculture/#:~:text=In%20conclusion%2C%20crop%20rotation%20is,putting%20rotation%20systems%20in%20place.](https://tracex tech.com/5-benefits-of-crop-rotation-for-sustainable-agriculture/#:~:text=In%20conclusion%2C%20crop%20rotation%20is,putting%20rotation%20systems%20in%20place.)